

THE ROLE OF MATHEMATICAL NIGHTS IN FORMING STUDENTS' TALENTS AND WORLD VIEWS

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Abstract: In this article, information about the role and importance of mathematical evenings in the formation of the talent, political and ideological worldviews of students of secondary schools is presented.

Evenings held in secondary schools, therefore, math evenings, are a type of extracurricular activity that is very interesting to students and involves them more fully. Math night is usually held as a final event at the end of math weeks. Sometimes mathematical evenings are organized depending on the topics of lessons held in mathematical circles, or on the anniversaries of great mathematicians. In addition to mathematical problems, the math night will also have art pieces for the general public. The results of mathematical creative competitions and Olympiads will be announced, and there may be awarding events for the winners. These reasons lead to an increase in the number of participants in the mathematical night.

Mathematical evenings have a special educational value along with the direction of teaching and learning. The night affects the formation of students' scientific, political-ideological worldviews, and teaching them hard work. A large group of students is involved in the night, which means that they all learn to perform a common obligation. Such a common goal affects the children's familiarity with each other, brings them closer, and causes the growth of mutual friendship and companionship. A large team is formed for common work.

Students are given the opportunity to work independently while preparing for the math night. Sorting various mathematical problems according to the program of the evening prepared in advance, finding effective ways to solve them, independently preparing for the lecture, creating an exhibition from certain models of tools, visual aids, creating wall newspapers for each class. is done. Carrying out such work inculcates determination in them. The work of equipping the hall and decorating the exhibitions will increase the aesthetic sense and taste of the students.

The main topic of the mathematical evening is selected in advance. Some experienced teachers prepare several topics for the math night in advance. Among them, the final determination of the theme of the night can be left to the will of the students participating in the club. But this does not mean that the subject of the night should be chosen by the reader.

If the topics of the evenings held at the school are of interest to the students, if they correspond to the wishes and needs of the children, if the issues discussed in it correspond to the competencies of the students of grades 7-11, if the methods of conducting the evenings are effective, then the purpose of the evening is complete. can be achieved.

The analysis of the experiences gathered in general education schools can be observed that the weekends and evenings spent in general education schools in most cases are spent in this context.

1. Night based on the history of the development of mathematics. In these evenings, the concepts of mathematics related to the school program and the relationship between them, the history of the formation of laws and rules will be considered. An analysis of the development periods of mathematics in the ancient, medieval and modern times, as well as the countries that contributed to the development of mathematics, is performed. Brief information about mathematicians who contributed to the development of mathematics is given. It is better that the issues under consideration are presented in an interesting manner, suitable for the knowledge and understanding of students of grades 7-11.

In the next sections of the night, as usual, he will reveal the secret of mathematical sophisms and tricks, answer mathematical quizzes, participate in a mathematical relay competition, solve mathematical riddles, tell mathematical riddles and read a mathematical poem he created, a mathematical fairy tale competition, a mathematical continues with viewing exhibitions and presentations. The content of the mathematical night becomes interesting and attractive if theatrical scenes are organized based on the plot of the fairy-tale problems.

2. Nights with historical and biographical documents. Such nights are organized on the basis of the lives of famous mathematicians and creative works of mathematics. Sometimes these evenings are organized dedicated to the anniversary of a certain mathematician. Such dates are very rare, so there is no need to wait for such dates. It is possible to mention the contributions of mathematicians who formed and developed the theories considered in the mathematics school curriculum. The necessity of carrying out such work is also mentioned in mathematics programs.

3. Nights about the use of mathematics in other sciences, technology and life, in everyday life.

Depending on the content of these nights, topics such as "Mathematics and the Universe", "Mathematics - defender of the country", "Mathematics and the king of sciences", "Mathematics around us" can be set. The purpose of these nights is to convince students of the application of mathematics in medicine, craft and everyday life, and to show the possibilities of mathematics, starting from the work of mastering the universe and strengthening the defense of the country.

It is self-evident that the development of society cannot take place without the development of technology. It is impossible for technology to move without mathematics. In short, it is to convince students that it is impossible to live without mathematics in today's society.

4. Fun math nights. Such evenings are mainly held among students of grades 5-9. In addition to raising the interest of students, the work of promoting scientific information should be carried out at the same time. The program of fun math nights usually gives more space to short notices, math quizzes and solving riddles, competitions and speeches, and games. Sufficient attention is paid to an interesting and meaningful night. Sometimes, the organizers of the party, in order to make it fun, make the material that will be discussed in it unreasonable and increase the number of meaningless games. This cannot be allowed. Assignments for elementary grades offered at night will be boring for students of grades 7-11,

mathematics will seem like a game, a joke. Therefore, the content of assignments dedicated to such parties should be interesting and should not lose their ability to make the child think and excite.

Their themes are selected according to the types of parties. After the topic is chosen, the preparation for the night begins. This is a very important and thought-provoking job. Materials reviewed at night should not repeat the information known in previous lessons or group work. Also, it is better to choose material to watch at night that is rich, close to the heart (pleasant), and that is not familiar to anyone.

The purpose of conducting a mathematical night is to teach students to do independent research, to develop their knowledge base, and to increase their intellectual and creative activity.

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